

REDUCTION OF MUSICAL NOISE GENERATED BY SPECTRAL SUBTRACTION BY COMBINING WAVELET PACKET TRANSFORM AND WIENER FILTERING

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a new method for musical noise attenuation induced by spectral subtraction. The proposed technique consists in combining a wavelet packet decomposition with Wiener filtering. Simulations demonstrate how this artifact is reduced without affecting the original speech intelligibility.

1 INTRODUCTION

In many practical situations, the speech signal when recorded or transmitted is buried in an undesirable background noise. Speech enhancement by noise removal techniques constitutes an alternative to restore the original speech. The basic approach of spectral subtraction is widely used for speech denoising [1]. However, its main drawback is the apparition of a distortion commonly referred to as *musical noise*. In order to reduce such artifact, additional processing have been developed [2] by combination with other tools such as masking properties of the human auditory system [3], speech/musical-noise classification and post-processing [4], multiresolution approaches [5]

In this paper, another solution for reducing the musical noise induced by spectral subtraction is investigated. More precisely, the enhanced speech resulting from a spectral subtraction is decomposed according to a new scheme based on wavelet packet decomposition and Wiener filtering. This scheme is justified by a frequency analysis of the musical noise characteristics. The use of objective measures, the analysis of the speech spectrograms and informal subjective listening tests show consistently good results. This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes both the context of the study and the spectral subtraction principle. Section 3 is devoted to the musical noise characterization. In section 4, we propose a new scheme for musical noise attenuation.

Finally, in section 5, experimental results are given and some conclusions are drawn.

2 CONTEXT AND SPECTRAL SUBTRACTION PRINCIPLE

2.1 Noisy context

The noisy speech signal in the time domain $y(k)$ is modeled by the following equation:

$$\forall k \in \mathbb{Z} \quad y(k) = x(k) + n(k) \quad (1)$$

where $x(k)$ is the clean signal to be restored and $n(k)$ is the additive noise, statistically independent of $x(k)$. By using a Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT), a processing frame-by-frame is performed. Therefore, in the frequency domain, the considered model becomes:

$$\forall f \in \mathbb{R} \quad Y(m, f) = X(m, f) + N(m, f), \quad (2)$$

where m denotes the current index frame of the speech signal, f is the frequency variable and $Y(m, f), X(m, f), N(m, f)$ represent respectively the STFT of $y(k), x(k)$ and $n(k)$.

2.2 Spectral subtraction principle

The Spectral Subtraction (SS) technique was introduced by S. Boll [1]: its principle is very intuitive. Indeed, an estimate of the noise spectrum $|\hat{N}(m, f)|$ is calculated by averaging $|Y(m, f)|$ during the intervals where the signal is absent. A robust voice activity detector is then required. The resulting estimate is subtracted to the observation spectrum providing an estimation of the orig-

inal signal spectrum $|\hat{X}(m, f)|$ expressed as follows:

$$|\hat{X}(m, f)| = \begin{cases} \left(|Y(m, f)|^\mu - \beta |\hat{N}(m, f)|^\mu \right)^{\frac{1}{\mu}} & \text{if } |Y(m, f)|^\mu > \beta |\hat{N}(m, f)|^\mu \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Here, the parameter μ controls the speech intelligibility whereas β controls the amount of noise subtracted from the noisy signal. It is worth noting that the phase of the noisy speech is not modified. Finally, once the estimator $|\hat{X}(m, f)|$ is obtained, the inverse STFT is applied to get the estimator $\hat{x}(k)$.

3 MUSICAL NOISE CHARACTERIZATION

The main problem in SS remains in the distortions caused by the errors of estimation of the power spectral density of the noise. These nonlinear artefacts appear as a “musical” noise disturbing the listener. The first step of this study consists in localizing in the frequency domain the musical tone using the very useful tool of Wavelet Packet (WP) transform [6].

3.1 Wavelet packet decomposition

Before going on, let’s give a brief presentation of the WP decomposition. It is based on a filter banks structure. A low-pass filter $\mathcal{H}$ and a high-pass filter $\mathcal{G}$ are convolved with the analyzed signal $y(k)$ and the results of these convolutions are subsequently decimated. Thus, the signal $y(k)$ is decomposed into an approximation coefficients $C_{1,0}^y(k)$ and detail coefficients $C_{1,1}^y(k)$. Both approximation signal and detail signal are iteratively processed over N stages. After N analysis stages, a tree-structured representation of the input signal is generated, composed by 2^N wavepackets $C_{i,j}^y(k)$ at scale i and at frequency j . The analysis filter bank is associated to a dual synthesis filter bank: a low-pass filter $\tilde{\mathcal{H}}$ and a high-pass $\tilde{\mathcal{G}}$ are combined with interpolators in order to reconstruct the signal.

3.2 Musical noise localization

In order to localize the frequential components of the musical noise, we carry out the following simulation. An additive white Gaussian noise is added to the phonetically balanced sentence in french language “Il se garantira du froid avec ce bon capuchon”. The sampling frequency is set to 16 kHz and the amplitude signal range is $[-1, 1]$. The initial value of the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) is 14 dB. The SS is carried out with the following parameters values: $\mu = 2$ and $\beta = 1.9$. Non-overlapping frames containing 512 samples are used. The STFT is performed after weighting the data by a Hanning window. The voice activity detector based on the observa-

tion cepstrum as reported in [7] is used. WP decompositions of respectively the original signal $x(k)$ and the signal $\hat{x}(k)$ obtained after a SS are performed over two stages ($N = 2$). Figure 1 represents the power spectral density of each WP coefficients. Curve (1) corresponds to the approximation signals, curves (2), (3), (4) represent the detail signals. This figure shows that the approximation signals of $x(k)$ and $\hat{x}(k)$ are basically the same but the corresponding detail signals are different. The difference is more significant for the high frequency components. Therefore, we can deduce that the musical noise is isolated in the detail coefficients. Its importance depends on its position in the decomposition tree. This conclusion is corroborated by listening tests. In fact, the musical noise is disturbing essentially in detail coefficients related to the deepest nodes of the decomposition tree. Furthermore, in each detail branch (i, j) , it can be considered as an additive noise $C_{i,j}^{n'}$: $C_{i,j}^{\hat{x}} = C_{i,j}^x + C_{i,j}^{n'}$. Although this hypothesis is not rigorously demonstrated, it can be corroborated by the following method of musical noise attenuation we propose.

4 PROPOSED SCHEME FOR MUSICAL NOISE REDUCTION

A simple but efficient idea to reduce the musical effect of the spectral technique is to proceed to a WP decomposition of the restored signal by SS $\hat{x}(k)$. The approximation signal $C_{N,0}^{\hat{x}}(k)$ remains unchanged. Each detail coefficient $C_{i,j}^{\hat{x}}(k)$ is filtered by a Wiener filter. The inverse WP decomposition is then applied leading to a restored signal $\tilde{x}(k)$ (Fig. 2). Let’s recall that the Wiener filter $H_{i,j}(m, f)$ is the linear filter which minimizes the Mean Square Error (MSE) [8]. For the WP detail coefficient (i, j) in the frame m , the frequency response $H_{i,j}(m, f)$ of the Wiener filter is obtained by

$$H_{i,j}(m, f) = \frac{\hat{P}_{C_{i,j}^{\hat{x}}}(m, f)}{\hat{P}_{C_{i,j}^{\hat{x}}}(m, f) + \hat{P}_{C_{i,j}^{n'}}(m, f)} \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{P}_{C_{i,j}^{\hat{x}}}(m, f)$ and $\hat{P}_{C_{i,j}^{n'}}(m, f)$ are respectively power spectral density estimates of the detail coefficients of $\hat{x}(k)$ and $n'(k)$.

The main advantage of the proposed scheme is the considerable reduction of the musical noise *without* affecting the original speech intelligibility. In fact, the auditive quality is then improved and the value of the final MSE $E[x(k) - \hat{x}(k)]^2$ is decreased. These conclusions are illustrated in the next section.

5 PERFORMANCES

Two noisy context are tested. The first one corresponds to the already used speech signal disturbed by Gaussian

noise. The second one is associated with a real-life environment. The speech signal is recorded in a running car at a velocity of 140 km/h. It is disturbed by both an external noise and an acoustic echo. The acoustic echo is reduced using the Normalized Least Mean Square (NLMS) adaptive algorithm.

5.1 Effect of number of decomposition stages

The number of decomposition stages N is a determining factor for a good quality of denoising. Figure 3 illustrates the evolution of the MSE *versus* N for the two tested contexts. Curve (a) is obtained in case of additive gaussian noise, curve (b) is obtained when dealing with acoustic echo. Note that $N = 0$ corresponds to the classical SS technique. These curves show that for each context, the MSE decreases as N increases until an optimal value ($N = 3$ for case (a) and $N = 5$ for case (b)). After that, the performances are degraded. It is important to note that although the relatively low rate of improvement, the auditive quality is more pleasant.

5.2 Improvement of musical noise effect

We compare the spectrograms of the enhanced speeches obtained with SS and our method. Figure 4-(1) shows the spectrogram of the original speech. Figure 4-(2) shows the spectrogram of the noisy speech. Figure 4-(3) shows the spectrogram of the enhanced speech obtained by SS. Figure 4-(4) shows the spectrogram of the enhanced speech obtained by our method.

In Figure 4-(3), the musical tone appears as isolated peaks and short ridges which are randomly distributed in the spectrogram. Figure 4-(4) represents the spectrogram of the restored speech signal using the proposed scheme. As expected, the unwanted short stripes are reduced and the speech contents is preserved.

5.3 Comparison between classical schemes and the proposed one

A comparative study between monoresolution schemes (spectral subtraction and Wiener filtering) and multiresolution schemes (the well known Donoho's technique based on WP followed by soft and hard thresholding [9], a WP decomposition followed by Wiener filters and the proposed method) is presented in table (1). These results prove the effectiveness of the proposed scheme. In fact, Donoho's shrinkage technique is not adapted for speech signal and the monoresolution techniques are improved by the use of WP decomposition.

6 CONCLUSION

In this work, a novel approach for musical noise reduction generated by spectral subtraction is proposed. The

proposed scheme is based on wavelet packet decomposition and Wiener filtering principle. In fact, a multiresolution localization of frequential components of musical noise permits to justify such scheme. Performances assessment based on spectrogram plots, objective measures and informal subjective listening tests show that our method gives consistently good results.

References

- [1] S. F. Boll, "Suppression of Acoustic Noise in Speech Using Spectral Subtraction," IEEE Trans. Acoust., Speech, Signal Processing, vol. ASSP-27, pp. 113-120, April 1979.
- [2] J. S. Lim and A. V. Oppenheim, "Enhancement and Bandwidth Compression of Noisy Speech," Proc. IEEE, vol. 67, pp. 1586-1604, December 1979.
- [3] N. Virag, "Single Channel Speech Enhancement Based on Masking Properties of the Human Auditory System," IEEE Trans. Speech and Audio Processing, vol. 7, pp. 126-137, March 1999.
- [4] Z. Goh, K. Tan, B.T.G Tan, "Postprocessing Method for Suppressing Musical Noise Generated by Spectral Subtraction," IEEE Trans. Speech and Audio Processing, vol. 6, pp. 287-292, May 1998.
- [5] T. Gulzow, A. Engelsberg, U. Heute, "Comparison of a Discrete Wavelet Transformation and a Nonuniform Polyphase Filterbank Applied to Spectral Subtraction Speech Enhancement", Signal Processing, Special Issue on Acoustic Echo and Noise Control, vol. 64, pp 5-19, January 1998.
- [6] M.V. Wickerhauser, "INRIA Lectures on Wavelet Packet Algorithms," in *Ondelettes et paquets d'ondelettes*, Rocquencourt, France, 1991.
- [7] V. Davidek, J. Sika, J. Stusak, "Implementing a Noise Cancellation System with the TMS 320C31," ESIEE, SPRA 335, Texas Instrument, Paris, September 1996.
- [8] S. V. Vaseghi, *Advanced Signal Processing and Digital Noise Reduction*. Belfast: Queen's University of Belfast UK, John Wiley and Sons Ltd and BG. Teubner, 1996.
- [9] D. L. Donoho, "Denoising by Soft Thresholding," IEEE Trans. Information Theory, vol. 41, pp. 613-627, 1995.

Method	Original	Wiener filter	SS
MSE (dB)	-30.27	-32.59	-32.69
Method	WP and Wiener filtering	WP and thresholding	Proposed approach
MSE (dB)	-30.45	-32.84	-33.41

Table 1: Comparison between monoresolution and multiresolution approaches.

Figure 1: Illustration of the musical noise effect on the Power Spectral Density of the WPD coefficients. (1): approximation signal, (2), (3), (4): detail signals. Solid line: clean speech $x(k)$, dash line : denoised speech $\hat{x}(k)$ by SS.

Figure 2: Proposed scheme for musical noise reduction.

Figure 3: Effect of number of decomposition stages.

Figure 4: Spectra of the following signals. (1): original signal, (2): noisy signal, (3): denoised signal using spectral subtraction, (4): denoised signal using our proposed scheme.